

The Key Positions in the Bangladeshi Readymade Garments Sector

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Abstract

Despite of poverty, high population and resource limitations, Bangladesh has been running with an emerging economy. In this economic advancement, the role of readymade garments (RMG) is significant. Not through the export, the sector assisting by employing over 4 million people. The RMG is the largest industrial sector of Bangladesh.

Unfortunately, the foreign nationals are working in the middle level, even often at the top. They are leading the sector. The lack of focus on the key positions in the RMG sector is the vital reason behind the unemployment of Bangladeshi nationals.

The paper aims at discovering the key positions in the readymade garments sector of Bangladesh. Such exploration will make the Bangladeshi people to understand where and how they can contribute. Hence, the employment rate in the sector will be increasing.

Key Words: *Readymade Garments, Key Positions, Remittance, Employment, Economic Development, Systematic Literature Review.*

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1.0 INTRODUCTION

Readymade garments (RMG) sector being a major part of Bangladeshi industries, have been playing a very crucial and critical role on economic development (Mia and Akter, 2019). In its ancient and glorious journey, RMG sector has been continuously maximizing the nation export volume, almost 80% of the total export (Farhana et al., 2022), (Islam, 2021). More significantly, the RMG sector creating scopes for employment for the wide range of people, up to 4 million (Islam, 2021), (Islam et al., 2016a). Hence, the RMG sector is directly impacting on the gross domestic product (GDP), through wide range of employment rather than export earnings (Uddin, 2014).

The research department (external economics wing) of the Bangladesh Bank reveals that despite the COVID-19 pandemic situations, the readymade garments sector has contributed 9.25% to our GDP in the financial year 2021-22 (Research, 2022). It stands at USD 42,613.15 million, surprisingly, which is 35.47% higher than the previous fiscal year (Research, 2022).

Though generating huge employment, unfortunately, from this vital sector, huge foreign currency has been remitting to the other countries through employments (Tuhin, 2022), (Noor, 2018). They are employed in key positions in RMG and textile sectors in the mid-level key positions (TextileToday, 2017) and being paid almost 20% extra salary (Noor, 2018) which causing \$2 billion yearly remittance to our neighbouring countries (Fazal and Ahmed, 2020). Hence, our country is experiencing huge deficiency in the foreign currency reserve in-spite of high volume of export.

A recent paper from the Transparency International Bangladesh (TIB) has revealed that \$3.15 billion are being remitted out of Bangladesh every year (Manzoor-E-Khoda, 2020). Not only that, TIB also mentions that this amount is often transferred illegally, as the many of the foreign workers work here on tourist visa and interestingly the employers are arranging such employment (Manzoor-E-Khoda, 2020).

TIB has also pointed out the proportion of diverse foreign residents working in Bangladesh as presented bellow:

Figure – 01 : Foreign Workers in Bangladesh; sources: (Fazal and Ahmed, 2020), TIB.

Bangladeshi researchers on many occasions have argued for adequate expertise to work successfully in the RMG sector (Hossian et al., 2019), (Zaman et al., 2018). As stated earlier, we have lacking in this area and the foreign people are exploring this opportunity, which results in huge foreign currency remittance from Bangladesh.

In addition, it has been found that the RMG sector has been unsuccessful in appealing the graduates from the best universities in Bangladesh. A survey has noticed that 68% graduates are unwilling to pursue their career in RMG sector (Fazal and Ahmed, 2020).

Altogether, it is critically essential to figure out the key positions in the RMG sector, as well as to change the motivation of the fresh graduates. However, in this dilemma, the paper is focusing only identification of the key positions.

This paper does not focus on neither reducing the foreign remittance nor arranging the employment for the Bangladeshi nationals. It only deals with identifying the key positions in the Bangladeshi RMG sector.

1.1 Research Gap

While the most significant sector of employment, the literature found a very few papers regarding the key positions. No previous research was found exploring the reasons of lacking of Bangladeshi nationals' absence in the key positions in the readymade garments, apparel and textile sectors. In addition, the reluctance and lack of job readiness of our graduates created the vacuum and that has been filled by the foreign nationals.

1.2 Research Question

This research attempted to explore the key positions in the Bangladeshi RMG sector, so, dealt with a single research question (RQ), as

RQ: What are the key positions in the Bangladeshi RMG Sector?

1.2 Objective of the Research

Considering the context and research question, the paper dealt with a single objective related to the key positions of the RMG sector in Bangladesh.

- To find out the key positions in the RMG sector of Bangladesh.

1.3 Scope of the Research

The paper was limited within the readymade garments, apparels and textile sectors. Furthermore, it focuses on the key positions in those sectors.

1.4 Limitations

Though the paper was very critical regarding the employment issues, where we were being passively struggling for reducing our high unemployment rate. But the time and cost were the major barriers. The bureaucratic systems often killed the most precious time for screening, reviewing and approving the paper. Another barrier, cost, was not very uncommon of the government institutions, while the country's economy fought back after the COVID-19 pandemic and during the war in the Europe.

1.5 Presentation Structure

The entire paper is divided into 5 major chapters; e.g., introduction, literature review, research methodology, findings and discussions, and conclusion. A brief of each chapter provided bellow:

1.5.1 Introduction

The background and rational of the paper well explained. After spotting the research gap, particular research question and objective were developed. The research scope and limitations are described in this chapter.

1.5.2 Literature Review

The literature review chapter included relevant literature. A systematic literature review was conducted with a review protocol for identifying the key positions in the RMG, apparels and textile sectors of Bangladesh. This SLR grounded the entire research work.

1.5.3 Research Methodology

Qualitative research approach was adapted in the research work based on the systematic literature review. For data collection purposes, focus group discussions were extensively used as qualitative research methods.

1.5.4 Findings and Discussions

Findings from the focus group discussions with the human resource managers or head of human resource departments of selected readymade garments and textiles were presented. The findings were discussed in the light and in relation to the existing literature.

1.5.5 Conclusions

The final chapter, conclusion, mainly included the concluding remarks. It explored the contribution of the research and prescribed the path for further research.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

Bangladesh is a highly populated country (Farid and Mostari, 2022), (Karim et al., 2022) with an estimated total population of 16.50 crore (Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics). Beside the burden of this huge population, the crucial challenge is employment (Mamun et al., 2020), (Siddiqui, 2019). This situation became worse as the graduates hold negative attitudes toward social entrepreneurship (Tu et al., 2021), but it could be a good solution for unemployment, if they occupy themselves in the RMG sector. Currently, foreign nationals are taking such opportunities and exploring the gap in the RMG sector in Bangladesh.

The huge number of foreign nationals employed in the RMG sector in Bangladesh (Tuhin, 2022) has triggered the paper. Therefore, paper aimed to figure out the key positions in the RMG sector in Bangladesh, because if the Bangladeshi nationals would be employed in those positions, the foreign employment would be reduced.

2.1 KEY POSITIONS IN BANGLADESHI RMG SECTOR

The literature on key positions in the readymade garments, apparels and textile sectors proven as very wide and the rate of irrelevancy is too high. On the other hand, different websites, e-magazines etc. revealed that the key or crucial positions in those sectors are line supervisor, sales associate, merchandiser, stylist, public relation specialist, inventory planner, retail buyer, accounts manager, cutting manager, fashion designer, graphics designer, textile designer, stock manager, packing manager, creative director, product developer, technical designer, quality assurance manager, production manager etc. (Sarkar, 2013), (Birt, 2023). The list of the positions seems to be irrelevant as all the positions are not directly connected with the readymade garments, apparels and textile sectors. Hence, it became a tough job to identify the true key positions.

Therefore, at this point, the researchers decided to conduct systematic literature review with a review protocol. This paper did not choose meta-analysis as it work better with data analysis and statistical discussions in literature (Paul and Barari, 2022). Meta analysis mainly deals with quantitative and scientific research (Haidich, 2010) whereas, this paper mainly focussed on positions, roles etc. which are very much qualitative issues (Zarghani et al., 2021), (Starr, 2014).

2.1.1 Systematic Literature Review

The systematic literature review (SLR) is a useful technique for finding out the most related literature for a particular research from the millions of scholarly publications (Nightingale, 2009) and positions as a guide to the researchers (Okoli and Schabram, 2010). The SLR has the capacity to handle the large and big data sets (Mikalef et al., 2018) and to analyze also. Inclusion and exclusion of scholarly papers are simply and scientifically handled in the systematic literature review (Xiao and Watson, 2019)

through launching a research protocol, and consequently, the systematic literature review has been gradually used extensively for synthesizing the literature and the body of knowledge (Kraus et al., 2020).

With such understanding, a structured, systematic literature review was conducted with specific intention to identify key positions or roles in the readymade garments, apparels and textile sectors across the globe.

For successful systematic literature review, it is a must to develop a review protocol (Benavides et al., 2020), (Xiao and Watson, 2019). Because such review protocol guides and assists the researchers to explore and find the required issues from the body of knowledge (Mohamed Shaffril et al., 2021), (Pollock et al., 2021).

Before turning into review protocol, an issue drawn attention. If searched with “Key Positions”, or “Crucial/Critical/Important roles in RMG/Garments” it returned either irrelevant papers or focussed on the role of the sectors in the country.

2.1.2 Review Protocol

A methodical, designed exploration of published scholarly articles carried out with the SCOPUS, Google Scholar and Web of Science databases. These 3 databases encompass the most current and relevant studies. A review protocol, mechanism for the effective search in the body of knowledge (Xiao and Watson, 2019), (Thomé et al., 2016), (Tranfield et al., 2003) established for exploring and pointing relevant articles/scholarly papers that discussed or narrated about the key positions in the ready-made garments, apparels and textile sectors across the world. The protocol includes following criteria:

1. Searching database with Google Scholar, Scopus, and Web of Science.
2. Search with “Who are the key managers in readymade garments?” and add additional 2 criteria, e.g., “key managers”, “garments”.
3. Search with “Who are the key managers in textile?” and add additional 2 criteria, e.g., “key managers”, “textile”.
4. Papers must be published in international journals as scholarly research articles.
5. Scholarly papers published during 2010 and 2023 only (Last 14 years).
6. Papers must be focusing on the key/important/vital/crucial managers working in the readymade garments, apparels and textile.
7. Papers must be published in English.

Important As stated earlier, the term “Key Positions” did not work appropriately. Instead of that, “Key Managers” worked better and revealed the desired outcomes.

Important Searching in ready-made garments and apparels yielded the same outputs.

2.1.3 PRISMA Model

Based on the review protocol, it has been proposed by the researchers that the selection procedure should be depicted through a diagram, called PRISMA model (Rethlefsen et al., 2021), (Welch et al., 2016).

Adapting the PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic-Reviews and Meta-Analyses) recommendations (Moher et al., 2009), following figure (Figure – 2) on the next page, demonstrates the way of gathering researches, which have been incorporated in the systematic literature review.

Figure – 2: Selection process for studies included in systematic literature review.

Initial investigation within the mentioned 3 databases (SCOPUS, Google Scholar, Web of Science), recognized 510 “title” and special criteria related articles during 2010 – 2023. After scrutinizing, titles and special criteria, 237 articles accepted at abstract level; where, 91 scholarly articles, with titles and special criteria – were selected for full-text paper. After careful full-text paper and examination of 91 articles, 12 scholarly articles were confirmed to include in the research. Table – 1 illustrates the summary of the SLR.

2.1.3.1 Selected Studies

Serial	Research Group and Year	Managing Director or CEO	General Manager	Operations Managers	HR Manager	Merchandiser	ICT Manager	Marketing Manager	Compliance Manager	R & D (Product Development)	Supply Chain Manager	Sustainability Manager	Logistics Manager	Designer	Sales Manager	Store Manager	Production Manager	Distribution Manager	Procurement Manager	Innovation Manager	Quality Assurance Manager	
01.	(Aziz and Ahmad, 2013)	√																				√
02.	(Amin and Hossain, 2014)					√	√	√	√	√		√										
03.	(Stabilini and Belvedere, 2014)							√			√				√	√	√	√	√			
04.	(Iqbal et al., 2014)																					√
05.	(Zheng, 2014)	√	√		√		√	√						√								
06.	(Perry et al., 2015)	√		√	√																	
07.	(Panahifar et al., 2015)																		√			
08.	(Sirilertsuwan et al., 2019)			√						√	√	√					√			√		√
09.	(Whitfield and Staritz, 2021)																√					
10.	(Dwivedi et al., 2021)							√							√							
11.	(Bag and Dhamija, 2022)										√											
12.	(Ye et al., 2023)					√				√	√		√	√	√	√						

Table - 1 : Summary of the Systematic Literature Review (SLR)

2.1.3.2 Positions Identified

After reviewing the selected 12 scholarly articles and analysing, the researchers identified a total of 20 key managerial positions as bellow:

1. Managing Director or CEO
2. General Manager
3. Operations Managers
4. Human Resource (HR) Manager
5. Merchandiser
6. Information and Communication Technology (ICT) Manager
7. Marketing Manager
8. Compliance Manager
9. R & D (Research and Development) or Product Development
10. Supply Chain Manager
11. Sustainability Manager
12. Logistics Manager
13. Designer
14. Sales Manager
15. Store Manager
16. Production Manager
17. Distribution Manager
18. Procurement Manager
19. Innovation Manager
20. Quality Assurance Manager

3.0 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research methodology encompasses research methods (collecting, analysing and interpreting data), research design (philosophical assumptions and inquiry procedures) and research approaches (plans and procedures ranging from broad hypotheses towards methods for collecting and analysing data) to solve the research problems or to satisfy the research question and objectives (Creswell, 2014).

Therefore, this chapter is not only concerned with the selection of research method(s), but it also includes the research approaches and the research design with the appropriate research method(s) to satisfy the both research objectives.

Scholars find that research methodology is a logical procedure that comprises all the actions engaged in executing the research, ranging from collecting data to analysing data for achieving a conclusion (Hathaway et al., 2018); and the research design (King et al., 1995) and the research paradigm (approach) (Wolgemuth et al., 2015) both are interrelated and are very important for reaching the research outcomes.

3.1 RESEARCH PHILOSOPHY

To begin with, philosophical considerations directly influence the research practice though these remains hidden in the research (Slife et al., 1995) and scholars have suggested to prepare explicit research plans with philosophical exposure (Creswell, 2014).

In his book, John W. Creswell, has termed philosophical considerations as philosophical worldviews which was an orientation towards general philosophy considering the nature of research that researchers convey to studies (Creswell, 2014).

To be more specific, the universal research framework is shown in the diagram below:

Figure – 3 : Research Framework (Creswell, 2014)

The postpositivist worldview considers traditional research arrangement holding more justification for quantitative research than qualitative research, while the constructivist view, often termed as social constructivism, refers to usual qualitative research approach (Creswell, 2014). On the other hand, transformative worldview is engaged in confronting societal coercion through embracing research investigation required for entwined politics and political revolution schemas, while the pragmatic worldview rises out of activities, circumstances and concerns rather than predecessor situations and is worried for applications that work towards problem-solving adopting both quantitative and qualitative research methods (Creswell, 2014).

3.2 RESEARCH METHOD

Considering the philosophical views, this research matched with the constructivism, e.g., qualitative research; because, it was categorized as an inclusivity research (Abbasi et al., 2016). As the research focussed on identifying the crucial positions, inclusiveness (Nilholm and Göransson, 2017) and explorative (Dana and Dumez, 2015) were the features of this qualitative research.

The key positions in RMG sector in Bangladesh are identifiable through qualitative research, because the paper belongs to social constructivism philosophy which refers to traditional qualitative research (Creswell, 2014).

3.3 RESEARCH DESIGN

Research design refers to the entire design of the research based on the research method (Dannels, 2018). Research approach, data collection method, research framework (Tobi and Kampen, 2018) and sampling all are encompassed within research design (Abutabenjeh and Jaradat, 2018), (Rahi, 2017).

Altogether, research design is the core of every research. In this research, the research designed as qualitative research with following research approach, data collection method, research framework and sampling.

3.3.1 Research Approach

Plans and processes are included in the research approach that narrow-down extensive assumptions into a precise way for collecting, analysing and interpreting data (Creswell, 2014) and selection of research approaches totally related and dependent on the nature of research problems.

The current research, aimed to identify the key positions in the RMG, apparels, textile sectors, it proposed as qualitative research. Accordingly, data collection method, sampling and data analysis plans were developed.

3.3.2 Data Collection Method

There are few common widely used qualitative data collection methods; e.g. in-depth interviews, convergent interviews, case paper, focus group discussions (McCusker and Gunaydin, 2015), (Wolgemuth et al., 2015), (Bhattacharjee, 2012), (Rao and Perry, 2003).

The synergetic effects as well as ensuring the outcomes (Rao and Perry, 2003) were regarded as the fundamental reasons for choosing focus group discussions.

Comparing the benefits and weaknesses of different qualitative methods of data collection, the research deployed *online focus group discussions* for collecting data. The circumstances of the current research sufficiently described, and in such situation, focus group discussions was the best to deploy (Hennink, 2013), (Moretti et al., 2011), (Bertrand et al., 1992), and it would be an enjoyable experience for the group members sharing their thoughts and insights, and as well as for the researchers (Colucci, 2007).

3.3.3 Research Framework

Research framework is a reflection of the research approach (Tobi and Kampen, 2018) that indicates the goal of the research. The entire flows of research activities are usually expressed through a diagram in such framework (Biermann and Kalfagianni, 2020).

The following diagram depicts the framework of this research.

Figure - 4 : Research Framework

3.3.4 Sampling

The paper conducted qualitative research where focus group discussions were the data collection methods. There are around 4,000 readymade garments in Bangladesh (BIDA, 2022). Participants for focus group discussions were randomly selected as referred to the simple sampling technique (Cochran, 2007). Apart from this it ensured that participation of at least couple of giant RMG factories support the sampling effectively (Sharma, 2017).

The ideal number of a focus group ranges from 6 to 8 (Robinson, 2020), (Krueger et al., 2000) which can be extended up to 12 (Khan et al., 1991). This research engaged 10 participants in the focus group discussion.

3.3.5 Sampling Frame

All the ready-made garments factories, apparels and textile mills registered with either Bangladesh Garment Manufacturers and Exporters Association (BGMEA) or Bangladesh Knitwear Manufacturers and Exporters Association (BKMEA) or Bangladesh Textile Mills Association (BTMA) considered as the sampling frame in this paper.

Currently, over 4,000 ready-made garments and apparels factories are running in Bangladesh (source: BGMEA and BIDA) along with 1,780 textile mills (source: BTMA).

3.3.6 Paper Location

The paper covers all the readymade garments, apparels and textiles registered with BGMEA, BKMEA and BMTA in Bangladesh.

3.3.7 Respondent Groups

The divisional heads, or at least the assistant managers of the human resource department were the respondents for this research. They participated in the focus group discussions.

3.3.8 Data Analysis Plan

The research collected information through focus group discussions. The qualitative data, derived from the FGDs, analysed qualitatively and manually.

4.0 FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

Triggered by a well-composed research methodology, the researchers conducted focus group discussion (FDG) with the head or manager or assistant managers of different ready-made garments. A list of participating respondents is attached in appendices. But for confidentiality of the research, the names of the respondents were not disclosed.

In the FGD, the respondents were provided with a list of possible key positions based on the outcome from the systematic literature review. The participants were free to add new position(s), if they realized and experienced essential. The main activity was to identify the most crucial positions through a ranking exercise (table – 6, appendices).

The findings and discussions were presented in separate section, while the findings were bit elaborated with little analysis.

4.1 FINDINGS

There was a very successful and enthusiastic focus group discussion regarding the key positions in the ready-made garments (RMG) sector of Bangladesh. The findings of focus group discussion described in separate sub-section.

4.1.1 Different Key Positions in the Bangladeshi RMG sector

The focus group discussion on finalizing key positions in Bangladeshi RMG sector was very interesting. 10 human resource managers of different level from different ready-made garments and textile actively participated.

In addition to the list provided of 20 key positions, they added 4 more positions, chief operating officer (COO), maintenance manager, fire and safety managers, and lab technician (or sample manager).

Within the provided list, the focus group participants also triggered couple of changes. According to them, when an organization operates multiple plants, there are positions of plant managers; alternatively, if it is a single plant garments, the general manager position is equivalent to plant manager. Therefore, the research adopted plant manager as alternative to general manager. Similarly, in case of small organizations, they argued executive director (ED) is more appropriate than chief executive officer (CEO). Hence, the position of ED considered as alternative to CEO. The changes and new added positions, as compared to position derived from the systematic literature is as follow:

	FGD Identified Positions	SLR Identified Positions
01.	Managing Director or CEO or ED	Managing Director or CEO
02.	Chief Operating Officer (COO)	
03.	General Manager or Plant Manager	General Manager
04.	Operations Managers	Operations Managers
05.	Human Resource (HR) Manager	Human Resource (HR) Manager
06.	Merchandiser	Merchandiser
07.	ICT Manager	ICT Manager
08.	Marketing Manager	Marketing Manager
09.	Compliance Manager	Compliance Manager
10.	R & D or Product Development	R & D or Product Development
11.	Supply Chain Manager	Supply Chain Manager
12.	Sustainability Manager	Sustainability Manager
13.	Logistics Manager	Logistics Manager
14.	Designer	Designer
15.	Sales Manager	Sales Manager
16.	Store Manager	Store Manager
17.	Production Manager	Production Manager
18.	Distribution Manager	Distribution Manager
19.	Procurement Manager	Procurement Manager
20.	Innovation Manager	Innovation Manager
21.	Quality Assurance Manager	Quality Assurance Manager
22.	Maintenance Manager	
23.	Fire Safety Manager	
24.	Lab Technician (Sample)	

Table - 2 : Comparison Literature and FGD Findings

Though the discussions were successful about exploring different positions in Bangladeshi RMG sector, but accordingly first objective of this research, it was a must to identify the key positions in Bangladeshi context. All the practicing human resource professionals were doing exercise for finding the key positions.

After finalizing the list of key positions, the participants were asked to rank each position from 1 to 10 – where 1 was for the most crucial position and 10 was for the least. Table – 3 illustrates the ranking of each position from 10 focus group participants.

		P - 1	P - 2	P - 3	P - 4	P - 5	P - 6	P - 7	P - 8	P - 9	P - 10
SL	Positions	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
01.	Managing Director or CEO or ED	8	1	1							
02.	Chief Operating Officer (COO)		8	1							
03.	General Manager / Plant Manager		2	7							
04.	Operations Managers	1	2		4	1	1	1			
05.	Human Resource (HR) Manager		1	2	3	1		2			1
06.	Merchandiser	2	1		4	2	1				
07.	ICT Manager				2	2	2		2	2	
08.	Marketing Manager	2	1		1		2		1		2
09.	Compliance Manager			2	2	2	1	2			1
10.	R & D or Product Development		1	1	3	2		1	1	1	
11.	Supply Chain Manager				3	2	1	2	2		
12.	Sustainability Manager			1	2	2	1	3			1
13.	Logistics Manager					2		2	1	3	1
14.	Designer					1	3	2	2	1	1
15.	Sales Manager	1									2
16.	Store Manager					5	1	2	1	1	
17.	Production Manager	1			3	4	1	1			
18.	Distribution Manager									2	1
19.	Procurement Manager				2	2	2	1	1		
20.	Innovation Manager			1	2	1	1		2	1	
21.	Quality Assurance Manager				1	3	3	2	1		
22.	Maintenance Manager				1	3	2	2	1		1
23.	Fire Safety Manager				1	3	1	3			2
24.	Lab Technician (Sample Manager)				1	1	2	2	3	1	

Table - 3 : Position Ranking by FG Participants

Firstly, it was counted that which position was ranked how many times at different scales. For example, for the Managing Director or CEO or ED, it was as follows:

The position, Managing Director or CEO or ED, was counted 8 times at number 1, 1 time at number 2 and 1 time at number 3.

Secondly, based on the ranking of different positions in table – 5, weighted average was accumulated for each position. All rank 1 was valued as 10, 2 as 9, and thus 10 as 1. For example, in case of the Managing Director or CEO or ED, the calculation was as follows:

**The position, Managing Director or CEO or ED, was counted 8 times X 10, 1 time X 9 and 1 time X 8 = 97
Weighted Average: Score divided by number of respondents
Weighted Average for Managing Director or CEO or ED was 9.70**

The following table shows all positions with weighed average value which represents the importance of that position.

SL	POSITIONS	WEIGHED AVERAGE
01.	Managing Director or CEO or ED	9.70
02.	Chief Operating Officer (COO)	8.00
03.	General Manager or Plant Manager	7.40
04.	Operations Managers	7.10
05.	HR Manager	6.10
06.	Merchandiser	7.40
07.	ICT Manager	4.60
08.	Marketing Manager	5.10
09.	Compliance Manager	5.60
10.	R & D or Product Development	5.90
11.	Supply Chain Manager	5.20
12.	Sustainability Manager	5.20
13.	Logistics Manager	3.00
14.	Designer	3.80
15.	Sales Manager	1.20
16.	Store Manager	4.80
17.	Production Manager	6.40
18.	Distribution Manager	0.50
19.	Procurement Manager	4.30
20.	Innovation Manager	4.10
21.	Quality Assurance Manager	5.10
22.	Maintenance Manager	4.70
23.	Fire Safety Manager	4.40
24.	Lab Technician (Sample Manager)	4.20

Table – 4 : Weighed Average for Different Position Identified by FG Participants

4.2 KEY POSITIONS IN BANGLADESHI RMG SECTOR

Considering the views, insights and experience of the participants in first focus group discussion along with the calculated weighted average, the most significant positions in the ready-made garments in Bangladesh are listed bellow in order of importance:

- 1.** Managing Director or Chief Executive Officer (CEO) or Executive Director (ED)
- 2.** Chief Operating Officer (COO)
- 3.** General Manager or Plan Manager
- 4.** Merchandiser
- 5.** Operations Managers
- 6.** Production Manager
- 7.** Human Resource (HR) Manager
- 8.** Research and Development and/or Product Development
- 9.** Compliance Manager
- 10.** Supply Chain Manager
- 11.** Sustainability Manager
- 12.** Marketing Manager
- 13.** Quality Assurance Manager
- 14.** Store Manager
- 15.** Maintenance Manager

Other position identified and discussed in focus group discussions; e.g., ICT Manager, Procurement Manager, Lab Technician (Sample Manager), Innovation Manager, Designer; were excluded from the most crucial list. Concurrently, the rest 3 positions Logistic Manager, Sales Manager and Distribution Manager, were found very insignificant in Bangladesh context.

The further details made available in discussions section, later in this chapter.

4.3 DISCUSSIONS

The discussions section focussed on the findings regarding the key positions. Discussions included reasons for inclusion of the positions in the most important list as well the reasons for exclusion from that list. All the discussions were based on the focus group participants' thoughts and insights and then supported by the literature.

4.3.1 Key Positions in the Bangladeshi RMG sector

It was interesting to find that the 4 new positions were pointed by the participants in the focus groups. They added "Chief Operating Officer (COO)", "Maintenance Manager", "Fire & Safety Manager" and "Lab Technician (Sample Manager)".

Before going to discuss about the 4 newly added positions, it seemed necessary to focus on inclusion of "Executive Director (ED)" as alternative to "Managing Director" and "Plant Manager" as alternative to "General manager".

Typically, an ED is a paid director and also a member of the board of directors in the organization (Fuji et al., 2016). In smaller garments, who do not employ any CEO, the ED directs the organization and manages all the operations (Hossain and Rahman, 2022).

In the large ready-made garments, with multiple plants, e.g., factories, a position, called plant manager, is vital (Habib et al., 2022), (Maalouf et al., 2019). Plant managers are responsible for overall daily operations and productions in their plants (Gubler et al., 2016) and report to the general managers (Toldbod and van der Kolk, 2017).

Generally, a COO is the head of all operations in the garments factories (Rashid et al., 2016), particularly, when it is a group of factories, role of a COO is very essential and critical (Panibratov, 2015). The difference between a CEO and COO is administrative authority versus operational authority (Kim and Na, 2022).

It was sought by the focus group participants that maintenance managers supervise and lead maintenance processes and activities in a garments factory (Thakur and Panghal, 2021). Their roles are vital for smooth production systems (Ganesan and Uthayakumar, 2020), as well as for quality assurance (Ramachandran and Suresh, 2021).

Fire and safety are major concerns for the garments factories (Islam et al., 2016b). Hence, inclusion of their positions was justified. Lab technician or sample managers work with the quality of products at the very early stages of production (Vezzetti et al., 2015), so their roles are vital for quality assurance and innovation (Piippo et al., 2022).

When the participants asked to rank all the 24 positions in terms of important for the RMG sector in Bangladesh, they ranked Managing Director or CEO or ED, Chief Operating Officer (COO), General Manager or Plan Manager, Merchandiser, Operations Managers, Production Manager, Human Resource (HR) Manager, R & D or Product Development,

Compliance Manager, Supply Chain Manager, Sustainability Manager, Marketing Manager, Quality Assurance Manager, Store Manager and Maintenance Manager at the top 15 key positions.

In their ranking “Sales Manager” and “Distribution Manager” proven very insignificant, though the positions were identified through literature review. The participants argued that they did not notice remarkable activities of these 2 positions in their organizations. Since, the supply chain manager covers the responsibilities of distribution (Nurruzaman et al., 2016), and the merchandisers carry out the sales responsibilities (Zhong and Mitra, 2020), the exclusion of the 2 positions were very rational.

The “ICT Manager”, “Fire and Safety Manager”, “Procurement Manager”, “Logistics Manager” “Designer”, “Lab Technician (sample manager)” and “Innovation Manager” were not placed in the top 15 crucial positions, resulted from the focus group discussions. In Bangladesh context these positions either self-dependent or merged with others.

Firstly, the IT skills are mandatory for all the key positions in RMG sector (Nipa, 2020). Furthermore, almost all the ready-made garments factories are now automated (Liu et al., 2019). Therefore, ICT Manager seemed no more crucial in Bangladeshi RMG sector.

Fire and safety issues in RMG sector are often included under the wide umbrella of compliance (Ebekoziem et al., 2020). On the other hand, supply chain managers also play the role of procurement and logistics (Yang and Yu, 2019). Hence, the criticality of “Fire and Safety Manager”, “Procurement Manager” and “Logistics Manager” were reduced and excluded from the top key positions.

The role of designer in RMG sector, frequently carried out by either the production manager (Grandys, 2015) or the research and development (product development) (Ruan et al., 2017). Concurrently, lab technicians or sample managers or innovation managers were found within the periphery of research and development in Bangladeshi context (Hossain et al., 2023), (Parven, 2021), (Amin et al., 2019). Therefore, the decisions of removing the positions from the top priority list by the participants of the focus groups were not surprising.

In conclusion, supported by the literature and the opinions and thoughts of the participants of the focus group discussions, the key positions in Bangladeshi RMG sector went with the findings, illustrated earlier in this chapter, section 4.2.

5.0 CONCLUSION

The most crucial sector for Bangladeshi economy is the ready-made garments (RMG) sector. This not dynamic for its export orientation, the sector is highly vital for the employment opportunities. Through the huge employment, the RMG sector plays a vibrant role in the economy.

Bangladesh has been suffering very badly with high and increasing rate of unemployment. But Bangladesh has huge population. So, it is not impossible to train and skilled-up the large population and make them ready to participate in the RMG sector in wider scale. Both the problems of poverty and unemployment can be solved.

There are a few research works regarding the significance of the RMG sector in Bangladesh. Even, it has been found that the key positions in the Bangladeshi RMG sector are still under the dark.

5.1 RESEARCH WORK AND OUTCOMES

It has been noticed and proved that billions of US Dollar has been continuously remitting from the country through the employment of foreign nationals, as they are holding the key positions and driving the Bangladeshi garments. The research was inspired from this problem and attempted to identify the key positions of ready-made garments sector.

Starting with a systematic literature review, a list of key positions in the RMG sector was pointed out. The list was not completely matching with the scenario of Bangladesh. Therefore, the researchers decided to use qualitative research method along with focus group discussions for data collection.

A focus group discussion was arranged through zoom platform. 10 garments and textiles participated in the focus group discussion. Managers and executives of different levels of human resource department in those organizations actively and enthusiastically participated, and mentionable is that voluntarily.

The focus group discussions revealed the key positions. The participants in the focus group discussions, included 4 new positions. When they ranked all the positions, through weighted average calculation, 15 positions were found very significant. The exclusion of other positions was described juridically.

5.2 CONCLUSION ABOUT THE RESEARCH TOPIC

“The Key Positions in the Bangladeshi Readymade Garments Sector”

The selected topic for the research was very clear. It dealt with the identification of required key positions for employability in the Bangladeshi RMG sector.

The researchers explored the most significant positions through focus group discussion with literature support.

Identification of these positions could assist the policy makers in empowering Bangladeshi people to be engaged more for reducing unemployment rate as well as boosting up the economic growth of the country.

5.3 CONCLUSION ABOUT THE RESEARCH QUESTION AND OBJECTIVE

The research was concern about identifying the key positions in the Bangladeshi RMG sector. Hence, the research question was presented as

What are the key positions in the Bangladesh RMG Sector?

The research question was successfully and completely answered through identification of the key positions in the Bangladeshi RMG sector.

To answer the research question, it was the huge job to identify the key positions in the Bangladeshi RMG sector. Hence, the research question was turned into following research objective:

➤ To classify the key positions in the RMG sector of Bangladesh.

The objective was satisfactorily fulfilled through exploring and defining of the most significant positions in the RMG sector in Bangladesh.

5.4 RESEARCH IMPLICATIONS

The research brought out the most significant positions in the Bangladeshi RMG sector. The government, the graduates, the recruiters and the training institutions can use for their own policies, guidelines and development issues.

5.5.1 Contribution to the Body of Knowledge

The literature of the ready-made garments, particularly, in Bangladesh issue, has received a very rich and in-depth research on the key positions. Hence, it can be confidently claim that the researchers have enriched the literature.

5.5.2 Contribution to Practices

Practitioners of different categories shall be benefited from this research. The government can develop a policy for the RMG sector so that Bangladeshi people can easily capture the positions for employment. Simultaneously, the fresh graduates can design their own so that they appear as the most suitable candidates for the key positions in the RMG sector.

The recruiting agencies can use the positions list for redesigning their job specification with more clarifications. Different training institutions can use this list to design their training program so that the programs will be completely position specific.

5.6 SCOPE FOR FURTHER RESEARCH

This research has opened several significant scopes for the further research and applications.

Firstly, the key position list can be analyzed in terms of employing Bangladeshi people. Secondly, the list can serve a tool for developing job specifications and the graduates will be able to concentrate on the positions. Thirdly, and most important, based on the identified key positions a skills matrix can be developed to make the Bangladeshi people capable in performing the skills in the key positions.

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APPENDICES

A-01 List of Focus Group Participants

SL	ORGANIZATION	DESIGNATION	DEPARTMENT	1st FGD	2nd FGD
1	Bengal Knittex Ltd.	General Manager	Human Resource	√	
2	Chantilly	Assistant Manager	Human Resource		√
3	Dekko Legacy Group	Dy General Manager	Human Resource		√
4	Envoy Group	Manager	Human Resource	√	√
5	Epyllion Group	Manager	Human Resource	√	√
6	Fakir Fashion Ltd	Manager	Human Resource	√	√
7	Hameem group	Asst. General Manager	Human Resource	√	√
8	Hop Lun	Manager	Human Resource		√
9	MBM Garments Ltd	Assistant Manager	Human Resource	√	
10	Noman Group (Textile)	Manager	Human Resource	√	√
11	NR Group	General Manager	Human Resource		√
12	NZ Group	Manager	Human Resource		√
13	Pacific Jeans Ltd.	Manager	Human Resource	√	
14	PG (HK) Limited	Assistant Manager	Human Resource		√
15	Purbani Group	Manager	Human Resource		√
16	Sara Fashionwear Ltd.	Senior Manager	Human Resource	√	
17	SQ Group	Asst. General Manager	Human Resource	√	

Table - 5 : Participation in the Focus Group Discussions

A-02 Focus Group Discussion: Exercise

We would now like you to RANK these positions from 1 to 10 in terms of importance to ready-made garments/apparels/textile sector. 1 for the most crucial while 10 for the least. Just put your RANK in number in appropriate cell. You can use SAME SCORE in Multiple Positions. You can ADD NEW Positions.		
RANK THE POSITIONS		
SL	POSITIONS	RANK
01.	Managing Director or CEO	
02.	General Manager	
03.	Operations Managers	
04.	Human Resource (HR) Manager	
05.	Merchandiser	
06.	Information and Communication Technology (ICT) Manager	
07.	Marketing Manager	
08.	Compliance Manager	
09.	R & D (Research and Development) or Product Development	
10.	Supply Chain Manager	
11.	Sustainability Manager	
12.	Logistics Manager	
13.	Designer	
14.	Sales Manager	
15.	Store Manager	
16.	Production Manager	
17.	Distribution Manager	
18.	Procurement Manager	
19.	Innovation Manager	
20.	Quality Assurance Manager	

Table - 6 : Exercise in Focus Group Discussion